

PHRASEOLOGICAL GROUNDS OF GRAMMATICOGRAPHY

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Annotation: This article talks about the phraseological basis of grammaticography.

Key words: *semantic system of language, notional structure, philosophers and linguists, semasiology, phraseological, characterizes pragmatic classes.*

The problems of semantic system of language, notional structure of language units, correlation of different meaning types, methodology of researching them, and a number of other most complex issues of semasiology attract a particular attention of linguist-representatives of most varied scientific schools and directions.

The increasing interest towards the problems of meaning can evidently be explained with the correlation of a range of factors related to modern levels of theoretical researches, as well as the needs for practical activity of a man during the period of scientific-technical revolution.

Since ancient times, the issue of meaning has been the focus of the interest of philosophers and linguists. However, although the notional structure of the word has such ancient traditions and the questions about meaning have unchangeably caused many hot disputes since Aristotle's times, a comprehensive solution of the problem of the meaning and polysemy of language units is still a long wished and not yet achieved aim. It is doubtless that everlasting semantic researches gave feasible results and promoted deeper coverage of a range of problems connected

with the essence of language meaning, various approaches to principles of meaning typology, etc.

It should be noted that the level of modern cognition, as a whole, made it possible for linguists to figure out complex diverse connections of linguistics with other sciences, discover the inexhaustible list of the objects of researches in semasiology; and, what is more important, to see the organic relationship between theoretical investigations in this sphere with applied work of the language. It is getting more and more obvious that for the further development of all branches of applied linguistics, from teaching to the development of informational languages, it is crucial to work out the theory of semasiology [6].

Here the paramount importance belongs to understanding the word as an initial unit of different derivational processes of the language. Meanwhile, one should consider the fact that lexicology and semasiology formulate the lexical-semantic layer of the language. If lexicology studies the vocabulary of the language as a whole, the object of study of semasiology is not the language meaning in general, but it is a so called lexical (lexical-phraseological and pure phraseological meaning).

Semasiology studies the meaning oriented side of lexical (phraseological) units in the light of such aspects as the nature of the lexical (phraseological) meaning, types of lexical (phraseological) meanings, regulations of the development of word (PhU) meanings, and the classification of types of the changes in word (PhU) meanings [5].

For the optimal interpretation of the linguistic nature of PhU (in our case - phraseosemantics), it is required to initiate from the relevant word indicators – derivational basis for the formation of PhU from any structural category. In particular, we should take into account such word characteristics of a language as:

- the word has a sign nature possessing the ability to call the notion about a certain object on the basis of the conditional relationship between this object and a

known sound group;

- the word is the main functional – structural unit of the language that possesses semantic and morphological characteristics;

- the word has a complex semantic content that strictly segregates a concrete lexical meaning (peculiar to a word symbol) and general categorical – semantic meaning that characterizes pragmatic classes of words;

- in the content of notional word symbols, various semantic meanings are combined:

- 1) general for the whole class of words (grammatical meanings);
 - 2) categorically generalized feature that the word symbol entering one or another semantic grouping acquires;
 - 3) lexical meaning belonging to a concrete word symbol related to the objective range which is the reflection of objects and their relationships in reality;
- among all characteristics, the most general characteristics of the word is the categorically generalized quality, that the word symbol entering one or another grouping acquires, for example, depending on whether it denotes an object, an action, or a quality, the appropriate sense of the given semantic class of words is included into the semantics of an individual word

A significant hindrance on the way to further development of the main problems of semantics, to our view, is presented by the abundance of terminology and notions connected with types of meanings of lexical units. Moreover, we can hardly rely on the solution of disputable questions that the researchers of semasiology face as long as the object of the disputes and main initial notions [such as “phraseological meaning”] are not clearly seen.

Evidently, one cannot expect a full correspondence of views in the area of semasiology, which can probably be explained both with the objective complicity and with “non-observability” of the meaning of language units, and with the insufficient development of the main notions of semasiology [4].

It is also obvious that one can approach the issue of types of meanings from different perspectives. For example, taking into consideration the process of the development of the relations between lexical meanings, we can converse about the system of binary oppositions of the literary and figurative, free and phraseologically set, logical and expressive meanings, etc.

The symbolic situation presupposing various types of relationships including such as the attitude of a person to the symbol, of a symbol to a person, of a symbol to the objective reality, etc. can make up the basis of characteristics to the types of meanings.

Of course, many other systems are also possible, but for any of them, following the main requirement

–logical unity is crucial. In other words, regardless of the typology of meanings that the word has, all the meanings identified in it must have a common classification foundation, i.e. they must correlate to the certain system and simultaneously presuppose the opposition to other or others for each type of the meaning. On this condition any type of meanings picked out of one system cannot be correlated (in the same row) to any type of the other system. Their incomparability may declare itself in the absence of the general foundation of comparison (incomparability of the “inkpot” and the “free will” - N. S. Trubetskiy) or in identifying such parameters that admit intersecting, not mutually exclusive types (discriminating people into the French and women - A. I. Smirnitkiy). Subsequently, it is hardly possible to speculate about lexical meaning, intentional meaning, and pejorative meaning from the same perspective. The former presumes lexical opposition and proceeds from two main types of the meaning of language units, the second –intentional – proceeds from the totally different linguistic ground, and the latter does not exclude the possibility of interpreting it as a component of the lexical meaning, and therefore, it cannot be studied as a type of meaning opposed to lexical [3].

Such generally known truths would not be subject to talks if alongside with lexical and grammatical meanings, the term “phraseological meaning”, used as a type of meaning but not related to certain systems and which presumes some other, possibly not yet developed classification type, did not appear regularly in linguistic literature [2].

So, what is phraseological meaning in understanding of those who use this term?

We cannot, and it is unlikely to be necessary to, give the overview of all those works in which the authors discuss or just touch upon in passing the issues of semantic structure of PhU. Moreover, as we mentioned above, we deal here not with frequencies and even not with the essence of meaning type, but about the principles of identifying and discriminating it from lexical meaning. We shall consider the interpretation of phraseological meaning proposed by A.V. Kunin [1, 134].

A.V. Kunin [1, 251] offers a new typology of meanings and distinguishes three classes - morphemic, word, and super-word meanings that correspond to the three classes of linguistic units. Thus he presents the system in which language units from different layers are studied in unity with their sound (graphic) form and meaning (meaningful content). In this case, it is quite right to speak about morphemic, word (lexical), and super word meanings each of which can be considered in opposition to others, due to specific characteristics possessed by a given language unit. In such instance, it is naturally that phraseological meaning is also included into this system. Drawing out this principle consequently, it is logical to speculate on affixal (prefixal, suffixal) meanings as well, and so does A.V. Kunin when he includes the meanings of morphemes, words and super word formations (set expressions), and grammatical categories into the same group of material meaning bearers.

In word meaning, "depending on the word type and the character of their

correlation to the extralinguistic reality", A.V. Kunin [1, 163] singles out eight meanings. According to A.V. Kunin, lexical meaning features common nouns, verbs, and adjectives. In addition, names are characterized with nominative meaning, numerals - with numerative, interjections - with emotive, pronouns - with deictic, prepositions, conjunctions, and particles - with lexical-grammatical, and finally, - with lexicalcommunicative meanings.

The main types of phraseological meaning are nominative (see nominative meaning of names), nominative -communicative(see names and word-sentences), conjunctional, and communicative meanings.

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